

Multidisciplinary research on biogenically driven new particle formation in Svalbard – an update (SVALBAEROSOL 2)

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Keywords: Condensable vapours, new particle formation, secondary aerosols, Arctic environment, atmospheric research

Update of [chapter 7 in SESS report 2019](#)

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17831894>

1. Introduction

Arctic sea- and landscapes are icebound and remote, and the state of the Arctic atmosphere is typically thought to be natural and pristine. Yet, it is exposed to human activity, and our pre-conceived vision of a virgin and pristine Arctic environment is melting away as the ice retreats. The Arctic is rapidly changing and is warming up to four times faster than the global average (Rantanen et al. 2022). This, in turn, results in modifications of its marine and terrestrial ecosystems with consequences on the atmosphere (Serreze and Barry 2011).

Changes in the atmospheric composition can lead to modifications in cloud formation and cloud properties, which further feed back on the climate by impacting the surface energy budget (Boucher et al. 2013). In the Arctic, up to 90% of the cloud condensation nuclei (CCN) population can originate from freshly formed particles, as primary particle emissions are limited (Merikanto et al. 2009). New particle formation (NPF) is then constrained by the air temperature and the availability of gaseous precursor vapours (neutral or charged) to form and grow atmospheric aerosol particles through nucleation and condensation (Kulmala et al. 2004). In pristine conditions, the background

aerosol concentrations are low. At times, cloud formation can even be limited by the availability of CCN (Carslaw et al. 2013). Therefore, even small concentrations of condensable vapours that form new particles can play a significant role for the resulting CCN population. To fully understand the mechanism leading to NPF, it is crucial to understand the nature and source of these precursor vapours in an Arctic environment that is rapidly changing.

This work builds upon the 2019 SESS report (Sipilä et al. 2020), presenting substantial insights into the chemical and physical mechanisms leading to secondary aerosol formation in the Arctic atmosphere. Since 2019, long-term observations and field campaigns performed in the Arctic, and particularly at the Gruvebadet and Zeppelin Observatories (GVB, ZEP, respectively), in Ny-Ålesund (NYÅ), Svalbard, furthered our knowledge of the nature, role, sources, and evolution of NPF precursors. These efforts mark an important step toward a comprehensive understanding of Arctic NPF and its implications for the climate.

2. The state of precursors of new particle formation in Svalbard

Through targeted campaigns and the establishment of continuous monitoring programmes, several projects have advanced the understanding of aerosol formation in the polar regions, including Antarctica, the central Arctic Ocean, and land-based and coastal Arctic environments (e.g., Baccarini et al. 2020; Boyer et al. 2024, 2025; Jang et al. 2025). These combined efforts have delivered the most comprehensive polar datasets on NPF precursors and particle number size distributions available to date. Therein, NYÅ, particularly owing to GVB and ZEP, is established as a cornerstone observatory for Arctic aerosol–climate research.

Multiple mechanistic pathways of NPF are now confirmed, involving sulfuric acid (H_2SO_4 , SA), methane sulfonic acid (CH_3SO_3 , MSA), iodic acid (HIO_3 , IA), highly oxygenated organic molecules (HOM) and ammonia (NH_3). Observations have shown that either combined or alone (in the case of some vapours), they influence Arctic nucleation, which, considering the low aerosol background, particularly in the summertime, can have a significant impact on the Arctic climate. A 1-year record of the typical condensable vapours concentration (SA, MSA and IA) from May 2024 to June 2025 in GVB is presented in Figure 1.

Figure 1: Evolution of monthly median concentration of SA, MSA, IA from May 2024 to June 2025 at GVB

2.1. Precursor vapours: evolution, role and (fate) of the Arctic NPF

2.1.1. Sulphuric acid

SA has long been recognised as a central precursor in atmospheric NPF (Sipilä et al. 2010). This molecule can easily condense, due to its low volatility, and therefore initiate molecular cluster formation and subsequent particle growth. Classically, SA originates from the oxidation of sulphur dioxide (SO₂). In the Arctic, SO₂ is produced biogenically from the oxidation of dimethyl sulphide (DMS), itself produced by marine phytoplankton and bacterial interactions (Stefels 2000), however SO₂ can originate from anthropogenic combustion sources as well. During the sunlit season, DMS emissions rise with primary productivity and when sea-ice retreat allows exchange with the atmosphere, fuelling oxidation pathways that yield both MSA and SA (Jang et al. 2025). SA is one of

the most efficient nucleating species, especially when stabilised by a base (e.g., ammonia or amines, Kirkby et al. 2011). Figure 2 shows the early stage of nucleation between SA and NH₃ as measured at GVB during summertime.

Several observations across the Arctic confirm that biogenic SA concentrations increase during spring and summer (Figure 1, GVB), when biological activity resumes and solar radiation promotes SO₂ oxidation (Beck et al. 2021; Boyer et al. 2024). Interestingly, during the MOSAiC expedition in the central Arctic in 2019-2020, Boyer et al. (2024) revealed that the annual maximum of SA occurs in late winter and early spring rather than in summer. These observations closely align with the Arctic haze season, showing a strong anthropogenic influence on SA concentrations, particularly during polar night and seasonal transitions. The differences observed at the GVB site, can be explained by

Figure 2: Mass defect plot: Chemical speciation of naturally charged ion cluster on 19.8.2024 (Vaitinen et al. unpublished data).

differing locations: the frozen central Arctic Ocean reinforced by a strong polar dome versus the coastal Arctic site of NYÅ where extensive sea ice cover is rare (Gerland et al. 2022).

The duality in SA sources hints toward its evolving role in Arctic aerosol–cloud–climate interactions. On one hand, SA derived from anthropogenic Arctic haze dominates the annual cycle and can seed NPF during winter and spring, potentially influencing CCN concentrations even in the absence of biological activity. On the other hand, biogenic SA from DMS oxidation, contributes seasonally during summer and can operate in synergy with other gaseous precursors. In addition, the decline of sea ice will further impact the atmospheric SA concentration by boosting both anthropogenic and biogenic emissions with: (1) increasing SO_2 concentrations from more shipping traffic – as new routes are opening in the high Arctic (Schmale et al. 2018; Geels et al. 2021) – and, (2) increasing biogenic productivity from the ocean due to warmer ocean temperature and longer periods of open water (Ardyna and Arrigo 2020) causing increased precursor concentrations.

2.1.2. Methane sulfonic acid

Similarly to biogenically emitted SA, MSA originates from DMS oxidation. Its seasonal evolution in the Arctic is therefore tightly coupled to the polar light cycle and oceanic biological activity. During the

long polar night, biological production of DMS is negligible and MSA concentrations consequently fall to annual minima (Figure 1). MSA exhibits a pronounced maximum in late spring and early summer with concentrations that can rise by more than an order of magnitude from polar night to polar day (Figure 1 and Boyer et al. 2024). This coincides with the annual peak of chlorophyll-a concentrations at high latitudes observed in May–June as phytoplankton activity and air mass transport from biologically active waters intensify (Assmy et al. 2023; Hoppe et al. 2024).

MSA can impact several aspects of the NPF process in the Arctic. First, in synergy with SA, it contributes to the condensational growth of nanometre-sized clusters toward CCN sizes. Laboratory studies and field observations have shown that while pure SA-driven nucleation produces ultrafine clusters, the inclusion of MSA enhances growth rates under cold conditions (Beck et al. 2021; Shen et al. 2022), such as in the Arctic. Given MSA's presence in field observations of particle phase composition, its importance for the subsequent growth of freshly nucleated clusters by condensation is undeniable. Second, MSA serves as a marker of the marine biological influence on Arctic aerosol composition, with elevated gas-phase MSA coinciding with enhanced sulphate fractions in the dominating Aitken mode particles. Finally, while its individual role in nucleation is still

under discussion, continuous field measurements of the atmospheric ion composition are needed to fully understand its role in NPF. In the future, Arctic MSA concentrations may increase due to rising DMS emissions as sea-ice extent declines (Jang et al. 2025). Yet, the fate of MSA in the Arctic atmosphere remains uncertain as future scenarios highlight that potential increases in would lead to a competition between condensation (i.e., aerosol growth / possibly formation) and removal/deposition processes (Pernov et al. 2024).

2.1.3. Iodic acid

IA has recently emerged as a central driver of Arctic NPF, with field measurements over the high Arctic providing direct molecular evidence that IA initiates nucleation events in early spring (Sipilä et al. 2016). During the MOCCA expedition, Baccarini et al. (2020) observed NPF episodes during the autumn over the pack ice, depicting IA concentrations far exceeding those of SA (often by factors of 6–10). Therein, anion clusters of iodine oxides were found with up to eight iodine atoms, showing a clear signature of iodine-driven nucleation (under conditions with low background particle concentrations).

These observations tied the season's sharp rise in IA to the onset of freeze-up and a concurrent increase in boundary-layer ozone (the latter driving the oxidation of molecular iodine to IA), implicating both biotic (sea-ice microalgae) and abiotic (e.g., brine channel, snowpack and frozen saline surface) iodine release pathways across the pack ice (Saiz-Lopez et al. 2015). The full-year record from the MOSAiC expedition extended these insights, revealing the bi-modal seasonal cycle of IA: a dominant spring maximum and a secondary autumn peak, with minima in winter and mid-summer (Boyer et al. 2024). This pattern aligns with iodine observations at coastal high-Arctic stations (incl. GVB, Figure 1a), and points toward the synergistic action between solar radiation and sea-ice dynamics (i.e., melting and freezing) favouring production of IA via abiotic pathways. Furthermore, those datasets denoted that iodine chemistry relevant for IA production seems to proceed even under low light or even dark conditions when reactive iodine is available.

At the molecular scale, sequential addition of IA provides an efficient nucleation pathway, as observed at coastal sites. On the other hand, laboratory work shows that iodine oxoacids can also enhance SA nucleation by acting synergistically when both vapours co-exist (He et al. 2021). Together, the field observations and laboratory simulations frame IA as a seasonally modulated, ice-state-sensitive precursor that seeds ultrafine particles toward CCN-relevant sizes. Collectively, these results indicate that changing sea-ice extent and ozone will reshape the IA budget and, by extension, the frequency and climatic impact of iodine-driven NPF in the Arctic.

2.1.4. Highly oxygenated organic molecules

HOM represent a relatively recent addition to the suite of precursors known to drive NPF (Bianchi et al. 2019), and their presence and role in the Arctic are now increasingly recognised (Beck et al. 2021). Initially observed as products of autoxidation from biogenic volatile organic compounds (VOC), particularly monoterpenes (Ehn et al. 2014), HOM are extremely low-volatility products that easily grow particles but can also initiate NPF (Kirkby et al. 2016).

In forested areas (e.g., the subarctic boreal forest), their presence is undeniably associated with the local vegetation. In the barren Arctic landscape, however, they appear more subtle and may rely on the VOC fluxes from the soil ecosystems or marine emissions. Summer campaigns have aimed at detection of VOC at high latitudes. For example, in 2021, Thakur et al. (unpublished work) deployed field measurements using glass chambers around GVB to measure VOC fluxes from characteristic soil surfaces and vegetation around NYÅ. The results showed emissions of monoterpenes and elevated fluxes in the presence of vegetation (Figure 3) providing evidence of HOM precursors in the region.

Even if the exact HOM distribution and composition over the Arctic remain unexplored, HOM were detected up to the high and central Arctic (e.g., Beck et al. 2021; Boyer et al. 2024). They are also

Figure 3: Monoterpene fluxes around GVB (ng.m⁻².hr⁻¹): vegetation vs bare soil (Thakur et al. - unpublished data).

continuously monitored at GVB. Therein, HOM concentrations display a pronounced seasonality that reflects their dependence on both biogenic precursor emissions and oxidant availability.

During polar night, the absence of solar-driven photochemistry and low VOC fluxes strongly limit HOM production (Boyer et al. 2024). But with the onset of polar day and the continuing spring and summer, HOM concentrations increase as biological activity intensifies both on land and at sea (there likely owing to open-water biological productivity and sea-ice edge blooms).

Thawing permafrost and retreating sea ice are consequences of a warmer Arctic. With this perspective, a thriving vegetation both on the ground (Karlsen et al. 2024) and at sea will impact biogenic VOC fluxes and therefore the production of HOM, supporting increased NPF frequency and summertime CCN budget.

2.1.5. Ammonia

Overall, ammonia's role in polar NPF is essential in stabilising clusters formed by acidic vapours and

sustaining their growth to climatically active sizes (Kirkby et al. 2011; Beck et al. 2021). Through acid–base bonding, NH₃ enhances the formation and survival of molecular clusters by acting as a neutralizer. Laboratory and modelling studies have long established that even trace levels of NH₃ (in the order of tens of ppt) can increase the formation rate of SA clusters by orders of magnitude (Kirkby et al. 2011; Ortega et al. 2012). In the Arctic, where background vapour concentrations are extremely low, this stabilising effect is particularly important: without NH₃ or related bases (e.g., amines), many acid clusters might not survive long enough to grow into CCN-relevant particles.

The sources and evolution of NH₃ in polar environments are strongly seasonal and spatially heterogeneous. In the Arctic, NH₃ can originate from both local biogenic sources (e.g., seabird colonies, guano, tundra soils, snowpack emissions or even from the ocean – Wentworth et al. 2016; Croft et al. 2016) but also possibly from long-range transport from lower latitudes (Lutsch et al. 2016). Until now, the presence of gas-phase concentrations of ammonia in the Arctic and its implications for NPF

were only hinted at by qualitative analysis such as from the chemical speciation of atmospheric ions using mass spectrometry technology or indirectly from the composition of the aerosol phase. Direct in-situ measurements of ammonia are challenging to obtain at concentrations near the low limits of detection, which is relevant for studying NPF in polar environments. In these conditions, ammonia concentrations can oscillate by several orders of magnitude: from extremely low pristine conditions to short-lived bursts.

The substantial technological development in spectroscopy showed successful measurement of ammonia at low detection limits using the QC-TILDAS instrument (Ellis et al. 2010), even in the most remote regions (e.g., Antarctica, see Boyer et al. 2025), and have helped clarify ammonia's role in NPF. At the Marambio station, ammonia concentrations peaking at 13 ppb were associated with nearby penguin and seabird breeding colonies, while background NH_3 concentrations were less than 10 ppt.

While the Arctic lacks penguin colonies, analogous ecological sources—particularly seabird guano on the coastline (e.g., cliffs of Svalbard)—likely provide localised NH_3 hotspots, seeding nearby NPF and contributing to the local Arctic aerosol budget (Croft et al. 2016). Future measurements of NH_3 using the QC-TILDAS are on the 2026 agenda to catch the impact of the bird breeding season on the ammonia concentration in NYÅ. In the longer perspective, bird migratory patterns are changing as a consequence of climate warming. Fauna-driven emissions, such as those of ammonia, are expected to change in response. Coupled to the monitoring of condensable acid vapours and the chemical characterisation of ion clusters, introducing direct NH_3 measurement in the Arctic takes us one step further toward obtaining the complete picture

of Arctic NPF, and therefore will improve the predictions of NPF and its importance in the region.

2.2. Particle size distribution

Continuous particle size distribution measurements (particle diameter ranging from 5 nm to 700 nm) in NYÅ have enabled the characterisation of the frequency and intensity of Arctic NPF. Analysis of the particle number size distributions (Dall'Osto et al. 2019) shows strong seasonality, with NPF events occurring mainly in the late spring and summer months that coincide with periods of higher solar radiation and biological activity in the surrounding marine and tundra ecosystems. These events are marked by the rapid appearance of sub-10 nm particles, which grow over several hours into distinct nucleation and Aitken modes. The presence of vapours supports these growth episodes and increases the probability of survival of freshly formed clusters.

The deployment of a neutral cluster and air ion spectrometer and a cluster ion counter (NAIS and CIC, respectively, Airel Ltd, EE), initiated in 2017, has improved the detection of small particles and therefore extended the range of the particle number size distribution (from 2.4 nm to 40 nm), also including naturally charged atmospheric ions (NAIS: from 0.8 nm to 40 nm; CIC: from 1 nm to 5 nm). These observations bridge the molecular and climatic scales of particles by showing how clusters either grow into stable particles or are lost, and by identifying neutral or ion-driven NPF. Altogether, these instruments deliver critical closure between precursor vapours and cloud-relevant particles by providing the capabilities to inspect climatic trends on the evolution of the particle population and on NPF in relation to change in the environmental condition and response from ecosystem activity in Svalbard.

3. Contributions to interdisciplinarity

Advances on Arctic NPF have interconnected scientific disciplines. By identifying and characterising key molecular precursors, they provide critical insights not only for atmospheric chemistry and climate research but also information of value in ecology, cryosphere sciences, and modelling studies. Biogenic precursors must be integrated into studies of marine biology and terrestrial ecosystems. In the case of nitrogen-containing precursors, direct links with ornithology, soil sciences, and nutrient cycling can be pursued. In a broader perspective, the interplay of transported anthropogenic sulphur emissions with the Arctic chemistry also connects these observations with policy-relevant air pollution research and the development of new fuelling technologies. As an example, it has been proposed that ammonia be used as storage for “green” hydrogen and could also be used in future energy production (Menefee and Schwartz 2024), although questions about safe handling practices have yet to be resolved.

Immediate collaborations for closer links with oceanography, marine biogeochemistry, and remote sensing will improve our ability to trace the origin and variability of DMS-derived precursors. While contributions from ecology and biology were initiated to uncover VOC emissions from the Arctic tundra, the seasonal and spatial patterns of both

ammonia and organic emissions, and their link to seabird colonies and Arctic vegetation, respectively, need to be clarified.

Likewise, stronger integration with cryosphere sciences will further help to detangle the influence of sea-ice dynamics, freeze-thaw cycles, and snowpack chemistry on halogen activation and chemistry. These perspectives would enrich our atmospheric observations and enable a more comprehensive assessment of Arctic aerosol–cloud–climate feedback.

In conjunction with other polar research activities, the progress achieved has directly contributed to the SIOS observing system by strengthening the long-term multi-component aerosol record at GVB, improving interoperability between atmospheric datasets across the Arctic, and enhancing the capacity to integrate campaign-based observations with continuous monitoring. Looking ahead, the continuation of the monitoring of NPF and its influences in NYÅ – as a hub for interdisciplinary Arctic research – will encourage stronger connections with ecological, cryosphere, and modelling communities to fully capture the complexity of aerosol–cloud interactions in a rapidly changing Arctic.

4. Unanswered questions

Despite the substantial progress in identifying and quantifying key precursors of Arctic NPF, many questions remain unresolved. While we understand that the relative contributions of different molecular precursors, including SA, MSA, IA, HOM, and ammonia, vary seasonally and spatially, their interplay under Arctic conditions is still poorly understood. Specific to precursor vapours, further work is needed to characterize (1) the role of MSA together with NH_3 ; (2) the sources and emission pathways leading to IA formation as well as IA

interaction with other vapours; (3) the origin and characterisation of Arctic HOM; (4) the source and quantification of NH_3 in the Arctic.

Additionally, the contribution of NPF to CCN remains poorly constrained in the Arctic. The fraction of newly formed particles that further grow to CCN sizes, and their influence on cloud properties, remains uncertain. Continuous monitoring of the particle number size distribution and NPF precursors will enable improved

understanding of these processes in the changing Arctic. Finally, interdisciplinary gaps persist. How will changes in sea-ice dynamics, marine biological productivity, and terrestrial ecosystems reshape the availability of precursors? To what extent can cryosphere-related and ecological

processes be quantitatively linked to aerosol–cloud interactions? Addressing these questions requires sustained integration of atmospheric chemistry, ecology, oceanography, and cryosphere sciences through coordinated observations within the SIOS framework.

5. Recommendations for the future

- Continue the monitoring of neutral and charged particles at Ny-Ålesund.
- Implement continuous cloud condensation nuclei monitoring to link particle formation to cloud activation at all observatory sites in Ny-Ålesund (incl. Gruvebadet).
- Establish uninterrupted long-term molecular-level measurements of key condensable vapours and related ion clusters, with scheduled data submission to open data base (e.g. SIOS core data).
- Deploy in-situ measurement of chemical bases, such as ammonia, to resolve their ecological and seasonal sources, and thereby improve understanding of the impact of climate change on particle formation and composition.
- Support interdisciplinary campaign connecting atmosphere, cryosphere and ecology within the SIOS framework.

6. Data availability

Dataset	Parameters	Period	Location	Metadata access (URL)	Dataset provider
Mass Spec.	SA, MSA, IA	05.2024-07.2025	GVB	https://doi.org/10.71761/15d4f93d-8732-4bbd-86c7-2588c97b3680	Italian Artic Data Center https://iadc.cnr.it
NAIS	Particle (-) Ion (-) Ion (+)	01.2017-12.2024	GVB	2017: https://doi.org/10.71761/c160e115-a8c4-4516-8f66-0aea733df797 2018: https://doi.org/10.71761/41441030-6275-4a28-a689-467b50857aee 2019: https://doi.org/10.71761/1784047d-8ace-4bff-bbc4-e28819a146bf 2020: https://doi.org/10.71761/10af0c60-b531-4d3e-9d4f-64623b1743ec 2021: https://doi.org/10.71761/bac7dd94-f038-484a-86fb-e4a6a6404705 2022: https://doi.org/10.71761/37693d95-ced6-4e7a-b82e-8f30157244a9 2023: https://doi.org/10.71761/a91493e0-78cd-4c70-a31f-ddc1929d89d9 2024: https://doi.org/10.71761/55624457-d6ba-4e30-9765-2205b62bf4ad	Italian Artic Data Center https://iadc.cnr.it

7. Acknowledgements

This work was supported by the Research Council of Norway, project number 322387, Svalbard Integrated Arctic Earth Observing System – Knowledge Centre, operational phase 2022. We are thankful to the Virtual Laboratory for Molecular Level Atmospheric Transformations (VILMA), Research Council of Finland (grant # 346372 & 364230). We acknowledge ACTRIS CiGas-UHEL – Centre for Reactive Trace Gases

In Situ Measurements for providing operational support for the reactive trace gas instruments at the station. The authors thank the National Research Council of Italy and the staff of the Arctic Station Dirigibile Italia for their support in managing the instrumentation in GVB. We acknowledge support from the AWIPEV station (project numbers AWIPEV_0015, AWIPEV_0026) for ecological marine monitoring.

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(Photo: Christiane Hübner)

Gruvebadet measurement site in Ny-Ålesund, Svalbard. (Photo: N. Sarnela)

Multidisciplinary research on biogenically driven new particle formation in Svalbard – an update (SVALBAEROSOL 2)

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HIGHLIGHTS

- Cloud seeds form from different gases in the Arctic atmosphere.
- Several gases can make aerosol particles in the Arctic; condensable gas concentration is crucial to understand their impact on local climate.
- Ny-Ålesund is a cornerstone site for continuous monitoring of particle formation.

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Through targeted field campaigns and long-term monitoring, Ny-Ålesund (Gruvebadet – GVB) has become a reference site for studying the formation of aerosol particles in the Arctic. Measurements confirm that gases (either as neutral or charged molecules), including different inorganic and organic acids and bases, contribute atmospheric clustering (nucleation) and particle growth with synergistic but complex interactions. Their relative importance varies seasonally with (1) the impact of human-driven Arctic haze in winter, (2) the sea-ice dynamics during season transitions, (3) the awakening of ocean productivity in early spring, (4) the growth of the ground vegetation in summer, (5) and even with the arrival of migratory birds to Svalbard during the breeding season. Measurements of small particles reveal frequent aerosol formation events in late spring and summer, with atmospheric clusters growing up to a few tens of nanometres. In clean

Arctic conditions, these particles can potentially contribute to cloud seeding. Understanding these processes is crucial to forecast direct implications for cloud properties and climate. The societal relevance is clear: as Arctic ecosystems, sea ice, and human impact change, aerosol–cloud interactions will evolve in response and will affect climate feedback in the rapidly warming Arctic region.

RECOMMENDATIONS

- Continue the monitoring of neutral and charged particles at Ny-Ålesund.
- Implement continuous cloud condensation nuclei monitoring to link particle formation to cloud activation at all observatory sites in Ny-Ålesund (incl. Gruvebadet).
- Establish uninterrupted long-term molecular-level measurements of key condensable vapours and related ion clusters, with scheduled data submission to open data base (e.g. SIOS core data).
- Deploy in-situ measurement of chemical bases, such as ammonia, to resolve their ecological and seasonal sources, and thereby improve understanding of the impact of climate change on particle formation and composition.
- Support interdisciplinary campaign connecting atmosphere, cryosphere and ecology within the SIOS framework.

Instrumentation for new particle formation monitoring in Gruvebadet, left side: neutral cluster and air ion spectrometer (NAIS - Airel Ltd, EE); right side: Chemical ionisation (CI) – Atmospheric pressure interface time of flight (API-TOF) mass spectrometer (Tofwerk AG, CH). Scheme adapted from photo by N. Sarnela, modified by AI.

Mechanism of new particle formation in the polar region (a) Springtime, (b) Summertime. Abbreviations: DMS: dimethylsulphide, MSA: methane sulfonic acid, SO_2 : sulphur dioxide, H_2SO_4 : sulphuric acid, HSO_4^- : sulphate ion, OH: hydroxyl radical, O_2^- : oxygen ion, O_3 : ozone, I_2 : molecular iodine, HIO_3 : iodic acid, IO_3^- : iodate ion, NH_3 : ammonia, BVOCS: biogenic volatile organic compounds, HOMs: highly oxygenated organic molecules, GCR: galactic cosmic rays. (Diagrammes: E.-M. Duplissy)